

ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS FEEDBACK REGARDING SUMMATIVE THEORETICAL EXAMINATION PATTERN OF UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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Abstract

Background: Assessment strategies are a key component of higher education as they measure students' learning outcomes and academic progress. In undergraduate programs, summative theoretical examinations commonly include Short Essay Questions (SEQs) and Best Choice Questions (BCQs). Gaining insight into students' perceptions of these examination formats is important for improving assessment quality and ensuring effective evaluation.

Objective: To examine undergraduate students' feedback regarding the summative theoretical examination pattern and to identify their preferences and perceptions toward SEQs and BCQs.

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among allied health sciences students residing in the New Campus Girls Hostel, Peoples University of Medical and Health Sciences (PUMHS), Nawabshah. A total of 278 allied health students were included in the study using a non-probability sampling technique. Female students who were enrolled in allied health programs, aged 18 years and above, and who gave informed consent were included in the study. Students who were unwilling to participate were excluded. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire consisting of two sections: socio-demographic characteristics and questions related to the summative theoretical examination pattern. The collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Frequencies and percentages were calculated, and the results were presented in the form of tables and figures.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 21.48 ± 1.64 years. All participants were female allied health sciences students residing in the New Campus Girls Hostel, PUMHS, and Nawabshah. Most students were single, belonged to urban areas, and were from a middle socioeconomic background. Best Choice Questions (BCQs) were identified as the most preferred examination format. The majority of students perceived BCQs as easy to attempt, objective in scoring, and effective in assessing theoretical knowledge. Students also reported

that BCQs helped reduce examination stress and supported better academic preparation. Furthermore, a large proportion of participants favored a combined examination pattern, including both BCQs and Short Essay Questions (SEQs), as it was perceived to improve overall knowledge assessment and conceptual understanding in summative theoretical examinations

Conclusion: The study concluded that undergraduate students demonstrated a stronger preference for BCQs; however, most participants recommended using both SEQs and BCQs together to achieve a more balanced and comprehensive assessment. Incorporating students' feedback may assist educators in designing fair and effective examination systems.

INTRODUCTION

Assessment is vital for monitoring and verifying student progress, it's not only measure the knowledge of students but it works as a tool of progressing learnings to assess the students there are strategies improve teaching and learning identifying learning gaps enhancing deep understanding. Therefore evaluation is important for determining student's competency about knowledge, understanding and skills. An evaluation system rather than the educational objectives or instructional techniques shows actually what the students learn.¹The cognitive domain of knowledge is judged by theory and viva voice examination, the theory question paper are formed using subjective or descriptive questions. The descriptive include long essay and short answer type questions (SEQs), the subjective type of assessment includes Best choice questions (BCQs) based mainly on knowledge recall.

A medical student's learning journey is evaluated through theoretical, practical, clinical, and oral exams, with these methods providing timely feedback and encouraging effective learning. The evaluation should cover a student's understanding, capabilities, and mindset. Using formative assessments during the learning process to provide feedback and go on instruction, and summative assessments to evaluate final achievement at the end of a unit or course. By combining both approaches, teachers gain feedback into student understanding, improve their teaching methods, and help students identify their strengths and weaknesses to achieve learning goals. Assessment is fundamental to the educational process. The assessment of the competence of undergraduate medical students is

a very crucial mission. The following three learning domains are to be Assessment evaluated: knowledge and understanding, skill, and value. There are many methods for assessing the skills domain. They include a free response examination, long essay questions, Chapter short essay questions (SEQs), modified essay questions, multiple choice questions (MCQs), and others. MCQs emphasize mainly on knowledge recall, level I of revised Bloom's taxonomy; they can also assess a higher cognitive level when properly constructed. SEQs are efficient in assessing higher-order thinking and are associated with item writing flaws. Single-best-answer multiple-choice question (MCQ) or MCQ-Type A, comprises a stem, a lead-in question, and multiple options, requiring candidates to select the correct one. The quality of an MCQ item could be determined by three indices, Difficulty Index (DIF I), Discrimination Index (DI) and Distractor Efficiency (DE)). Both assessment for learning and assessment of learning play an important role in learning. Several studies have shown item analysis as part of quality assurance in assessments with determination of difficulty and discriminatory index in MCQs, relationship of item difficulty with nonfunctional distractors and have developed faculty development programs to improve the quality of assessments .Multiple tools for assessment are employed at end of year examinations in medical colleges affiliated with University of Health Sciences as per the guidelines. Medical Education department is being established in every medical college to ensure quality assurance in medical education.

Material and Methods

This study was a descriptive cross-sectional design conducted to assess students’ feedback regarding the summative theoretical examination pattern among undergraduate allied health sciences students. The study was carried out at the New Campus Girls Hostel of Peoples University of Medical and Health Sciences (PUMHS). Data were collected over a two-month period from 17 November 2025 to 17 January 2026, after obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB). The sample size was 278, calculated using the Yamane formula for sample size determination. The calculation was based on a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. A non-probability convenience sampling technique was used to select participants. Female students enrolled in allied health sciences programs, aged 18 years and above, and willing to provide

informed consent were included in the study. Students who did not consent to participate were excluded. Data were collected through a structured, self-administered questionnaire consisting of two sections: socio-demographic characteristics and items related to the summative theoretical examination pattern. The questionnaire was reviewed for content validity prior to data collection. The collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, median, and interquartile range, were calculated to summarize the variables. For inferential analysis, the Mann–Whitney U test was applied to compare differences in feedback scores between two independent groups. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The findings were presented in tables and figures.

RESULT

Figure 1: Age of respondents

Figure 2: Residence of Respondents

Table 1: Marital status of Respondents:

Marital status of respondent	Frequency	Percent
Single	277	99.6%
Married	1	4%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 2: Religion of respondents

Religion of respondent	Frequency	Percent
Muslim	249	89.6%
Hindu	29	10.4%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 3: Ethnic city of respondents

Ethnicity of respondent	Frequency	Percent
Sindhi	228	82.0%
Baloch	26	9.4%
Saraiki	13	4.7%
Punjabi	7	2.5%
Other Ethnicity	4	1.45
Total	278	100.0%

Table 4: Socioeconomic of respondents

Socioeconomic of respondent	Frequency	Percent
Middle class	249	89.6%
Poor class	23	8.3%
Rich class	4	1.4%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 5: Program of respondents

Program of respondent	Frequency	percent
BSN(g)	100	36.0%
DPT	70	25.2%
PHARM D	38	13.7%
BSHP	70	25.2%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 6: Academic year of respondents

Academic year of respondent	Frequency	Percent
1 st year	47	16.9%
2 nd year	82	29.5%
3 rd year	75	27.0%
4 th year	74	26.6%
Total	278	100.05

Table 7: Showing prefer exam pattern

Which types of exam pattern do you prefer?	Frequency	Percent
SEQs	66	23.7%
BCQs	131	47.1%
Both equally	80	28.8%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 8: Showing reason for preferring exam format

Why do you prefer this exam format?	Frequency	Percent
Easier to attempt	95	34.2%
Fairness in scoring	76	27.3%
Improves understanding	40	14.4%
Tests critical thinking	43	15.5%
Reduce exam stress	24	8.6%
Total	278	100.0

Table 9: Showing exam format that tests knowledge accurately

In your opinion which exam format tests knowledge more accurately ?	Frequency	Percent
SEQs	68	24.5%
BCQs	129	46.6
Both equally	81	29.1%
Total	278	100.05

Table 10: Showing exam format perceived as stressful

Which format do you find more stressful	Frequency	Percent
SEQs	84	30.2%
BCQs	133	47.8%
Both equally	61	21.9%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 11: Showing exam type that motivates deeper study

Which exam types of motivates you to study more deeply?	Frequency	Percent
SEQs	73	26.3
BCQs	143	51.4
Both equally	62	22.3
Total	278	100.0%

Table 12: Showing exam type for long term retention

Which exam types help you in long term retention of knowledge ?	Frequency	Percent
SEQs	93	33.5%
BCQs	109	39.3
Both equally	76	27.2
Total	278	100.0%

Table 13: Showing use of SEQs and BCQs in examination

Do you think a combination of SEQs and BCQs should be used in exam?	Frequency	Percent
Yes	222	79.9%
No	56	20.1%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 14: Showing use of combined methods in examination

Do think combination of both should be used in exam?	Frequency	Percent
Yes	222	79.9%
No	56	20.1%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 15: Showing preparation for BCQs pattern paper

How do you prepare for BCQs pattern paper?	Frequency	Percent
Thoroughly	131	47.1%
More deeply	147	52.9%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 16: Showing preparation for BCQs

How do you normally prepare for BCQs ?	Frequency	Percent
Practice question	155	55.8%
Notes other	122	43.5%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 17: Showing difficulty level of BCQs

How do you feel difficulty level of BCQs ?	Frequency	Percent
Mostly easy	29	10.4%
Medium	203	73.0%
Hard	46	16.5%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 18: Showing ways to solve BCQs

What ways do you to solve BCQs ?	Frequency	Percent
Elimination	84	30.2%
Keyword identify	148	53.2%
Guessing	46	16.5%
Total	278	100.0%

Table 19: Showing impact of preparation and solving methods on performance

Do you think your preparation and ways of solving improved your performance ?	Frequency	Percent
Yes	225	91.7%
No	19	6.8%
Total	278	100.0%

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to assess undergraduate students' feedback regarding the summative theoretical examination pattern, with particular emphasis on Best Choice Questions (BCQs) and Short Essay Questions (SEQs). The findings demonstrated that nearly half of the respondents (47.1%) preferred BCQs, whereas 23.7% favored SEQs and 28.8% supported a combined examination format. This distribution indicates a substantial inclination toward objective-type assessment methods among undergraduate students. The preference for BCQs appears to be strongly associated with perceptions of fairness, clarity, and objectivity in scoring. These findings are consistent with the study conducted by

Sachdeva R and Gupta A¹¹, who reported that students perceived multiple-choice formats as more transparent and less examiner-dependent compared to essay-type questions. Their study emphasized that objectivity in scoring enhances students' trust in the assessment system, which may explain the high preference for BCQs in the present research. In terms of perceived assessment accuracy, 46.6% of students believed that BCQs assess knowledge more accurately, while 24.5% considered SEQs more accurate. Interestingly, 29.1% reported that both formats are equally effective. This suggests that although BCQs are favored, students recognize the complementary value of SEQs. Supporting this, Kwon H-J, Chae S

J, and Park J H¹² concluded that MCQs are efficient in measuring defined learning outcomes with consistent reliability, whereas SEQs are better suited for evaluating integrative understanding and written expression. Their findings highlight that both formats assess different cognitive domains and therefore should not be considered mutually exclusive. Regarding examination stress, a higher proportion of students (47.8%) perceived BCQs as more stressful compared to SEQs (30.2%). This may be attributed to the presence of closely related distractors and the fear of negative marking or incorrect selection. However, despite the perceived stress, more than half of the students (51.4%) reported that BCQs motivated them to study more deeply. This paradox suggests that moderate stress may act as a motivational factor rather than a barrier to learning. An experimental study by Mee J ET al.¹³ provides further insight into this phenomenon. Their research comparing multiple-choice and short-answer formats demonstrated that while short-answer questions required greater cognitive effort, MCQs enabled broader syllabus coverage and encouraged systematic revision. The authors concluded that well-designed MCQs can effectively assess application and analysis levels when constructed according to Bloom's taxonomy principles. This supports the present study's finding that BCQs contribute to long-term retention (39.3%) and focused preparation strategies. Furthermore, 79.9% of respondents in the current study supported the use of a combined examination pattern. This strong majority indicates that student's value balanced assessment systems. Similar conclusions were drawn by Elsamanoudy A ET al.¹⁴ who found that modified essay questions (MEQs) demonstrated higher discriminative validity among high-performing students, whereas MCQs ensured objective marking and wider content sampling. Their study recommended integrating both formats to enhance reliability and validity in summative examinations. The preparation strategies reported in the present study also provide meaningful educational implications. A majority of students (52.9%) reported preparing more deeply for BCQs, and 55.8% relied primarily on practicing

questions. Additionally, keyword identification (53.2%) and elimination techniques (30.2%) were the most common problem-solving approaches. These findings indicate that BCQs encourage active recall and strategic thinking. A recent critical review by Ul Islam Z ET al.¹⁵ emphasized that high-quality MCQs, when free from item-writing flaws, can promote analytical reasoning and diagnostic assessment. The review further suggested that faculty training in MCQ construction is essential to maximize educational impact. Moreover, contemporary literature highlights the psychometric advantages of objective testing. MCQs typically demonstrate higher reliability coefficients due to standardized scoring procedures, whereas SEQs may introduce variability related to examiner judgment. However, SEQs provide valuable opportunities for students to articulate reasoning processes and demonstrate depth of comprehension. Therefore, integrating both formats aligns with principles of constructive alignment and outcome-based education. In light of these findings, the present study reinforces the argument that no single assessment format can comprehensively measure all dimensions of learning. BCQs contribute to reliability, fairness, and broad curriculum sampling, while SEQs enhance evaluation of higher-order cognitive skills and expressive competence. A blended examination pattern appears to be the most pedagogically sound approach for summative assessment in undergraduate education.

CONCLUSION:

This study concludes that the summative theoretical examination pattern is an important tool for assessing undergraduate students' learning. The findings show that most students prefer Best Choice Questions (BCQs) because they are objective, fair in scoring, and easier to attempt. Students also believe that BCQs assess knowledge more accurately and encourage focused study.

Although some students reported that BCQs are more stressful, they still considered them useful for improving learning and supporting long-term retention of knowledge. The study further shows

that students adopt effective preparation strategies for BCQs, such as practicing questions and using problem-solving techniques, which help improve their examination performance. Another important conclusion of this study is that most students support the use of a combination of BCQs and Short Essay Questions (SEQs) in examinations. This indicates that while BCQs are preferred for objective assessment, SEQs are still considered important for evaluating descriptive knowledge and understanding.

In conclusion, the study suggests that a balanced examination pattern using both BCQs and SEQs can provide a more comprehensive and effective assessment of undergraduate students' knowledge and learning outcomes.

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